

DEVELOPING HANDBOOK OF SOCIODRAMA TO IMPROVE INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS FOR JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract:

This development study is to produce a handbook of sociodrama to improve the interpersonal communication skills of junior high school students in the City of Kediri as one of the techniques that counselors can use in providing personal-social guidance services that are theoretically and practically acceptable. This research is a development research that uses the model of Borg and Gall (1983). The development procedures carried out are as follows: stage 1 (planning), stage 2 (product development), stage 3 (product testing), stage 4 (product revision results of expert judgment results), stage 5 (test prospective product users), stage 6 (limited product trial (small group test)), and stage 7 (final product handbook of sociodrama to improving interpersonal communication skills). Based on the results of the analysis of the assessment of experts and prospective product users as well as the revisions that have been carried out according to suggestions and input on the handbook of sociodrama to improve high school interpersonal communication skills, it can be concluded that the guidance for counselors is very feasible, very clear, very useful, very easy, very precise, very interesting theoretically.

Keywords: handbook of sociodrama, interpersonal communication skills

1. Introduction

Junior high school is a secondary education level in formal education in Indonesia after students have passed elementary school or equivalent level. In the transition from elementary school to junior high school, students adapt to their peers who come from different school backgrounds. Students communicate with their peers. They communicate with each other. Each student has different interpersonal communication skills. When students deliver a message to their friends, then their friend who receives the message misinterprets it causing misunderstanding between one student and

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another student. This misunderstanding is caused also because student interpersonal communication is unclear, and communication is not effective. Interpersonal communication is the process of delivering messages to recipients of messages with awareness to influence the attitudes and behavior of message recipients (Johnson & Johnson, 1991). In an effort to improve the interpersonal communication, skills of students in schools there are guidance and counseling services.

In formal education settings, especially in schools, counselors carry out responsive services, namely using individual counseling. Counselors also use group guidance services to improve interpersonal communication skills with expository techniques and group discussions. The group guidance service in question is sociodrama. Sociodrama is one technique in group guidance that shows students about social relations problems, to achieve certain guidance goals (Aryani & Farozin, 2017; Kellerman, 2007). Giving sociodrama by counselors or other experts to students is expected to improve students' interpersonal communication skills. On the other hand, there is no counselor who uses sociodrama techniques as a method of improving students' communication skills, so a handbook of sociodrama is needed as a method to improve student interpersonal communication skills in school.

The purpose of this research and development is to produce a handbook of sociodrama to improve interpersonal communication skills that are theoretically and practically acceptable. In detail this development aims to: produce a handbook of sociodrama to improve interpersonal communication skills that have usefulness for junior high school students, produce handbook of sociodrama for improving interpersonal communication skills that have feasibility for junior high school students, produce handbook of sociodrama for improving interpersonal communication skills that has accuracy for junior high school students, resulting in a handbook of sociodrama to improving interpersonal communication skills.

2. Literature Review

Sociodrama is a role playing aimed at solving social problems that arise in human relations (Eckloff, 2006; Kellerman, 2007; McLennan, 2008). Sociodrama is used to provide understanding and appreciation of social problems and develop students' ability to solve them (Stein, Ingersoll, & Treadwell, 1995; Zachariah & Moreno, 2006). Sociodrama is also a tool or method used by counselors to teach certain skills through modeling, and can be used to understand a person's behavior and change student behavior (Aryani & Farozin, 2017).

Interpersonal communication is the process of delivering messages to recipients of messages with awareness to influence attitudes, and behavior of message recipients (Hackman & Johnson, 2004; Singh & Lalropuii, 2014). Interpersonal communication is also a skill for interacting, exchanging information that allows each participant to be able to capture other people's reactions directly, both verbally and nonverbally so that mutual understanding can occur, and empathy with one another (Barbato, Graham & Perse, 2003; Beebe, Beebe, & Redmond, 2010).

3. Material and Methods

3.1 Research Design

This study uses a research and development approach, by adapting the steps of Borg and Gall (1983), namely: conducting data collection, (reviewing library materials, need assessment questionnaires, and interview guidelines), planning, developing product design, conducting validation design, revise the design, test the product (prospective product users), revise the product (according to the target and results of the prospective product users), conduct trial use (small group test), revise the product (evaluate the product work system to find out weaknesses for improving and making new products again), making mass products (final products).

3.2 Research Target

Needs assessment is a data collection activity that needs to be used as a reference so that products made by researchers are in accordance with existing and effective conditions. In collecting needs data, researchers used two instruments, namely: questionnaire, a technique of data collection conducted by providing a set of questions or written statements to respondents to answer (Creswell, 2012). This instrument is used to collect data on student needs, so the subject of the questionnaire that analyzes this need is students who are included in the study sample. This study involved students in one of the schools in the City of Kediri. The research sample was 24 students of class VII A. Interviews are data collection techniques used by researchers to conduct preliminary studies in finding problems that must be studied, and also if you want to know things from respondents who are more in depth and the number of respondents is small or small (Creswell, 2012). Things that have not been revealed in the questionnaire are revealed through dialogue or interviews with the subject of product users, namely the counselor. The type of interview used in this study is structured interviews. Interviews for this needs assessment are addressed to counselors for student data in schools.

3.3 Data Analysis

Data analysis techniques in this development research are of two kinds, namely quantitative analysis and qualitative analysis. Technical quantitative analysis is used when analyzing the scale of interpretation of the assessment format for the implementation of sociodrama. While qualitative analysis is obtained from the written assessment in the assessment instrument suggestion section when testing the product. Analysis of expert test and product user test (counselor). The data analysis technique used is to use the mean. Data on the results of guidance and counseling expert judgment, media expert judgment, and drama expert judgment, and product user expert judgment (counselor) consist of 4 types according to the assessment questionnaire that has been developed according to product specifications. The four aspects are usability, easily, accuracy, and attractiveness.

4. Result

4.1 Quantitative Data from Expert Judgment

After the researcher produced the initial product development design, then an assessment was made of the product expert judgment. There are three types of product testing, namely (1) guidance and counseling expert judgment, (2) drama expert judgment, and (3) media expert judgment. After expert judgment, the product is then revised from expert judgment inputs and suggestions. The results of revision of expert judgment products are again tested to test prospective product users (counselors). The following are the results of the assessment data and presented according to the respective expert judgment classification. Data from guidance and counseling expert judgment are as follows:

Table 1: Assessment of Product Specifications
by Guidance and Counseling Expert Judgment

No.	Rated Aspect	Average
1.	Usability	3.4
2.	Easily	3
3.	Accuracy	3.4
4.	Attractiveness	4
5.	Total Average	3.45

Table 2: Systematic Assessment Handbook of Sociodrama
by Guidance and Counseling Expert Judgment

No.	Rated Aspect	Average
1.	Introduction	3.5
2.	Application handbook of Sociodrama	3.4
3.	Sociodrama	3.3
4.	Closing and evaluation	3
5.	Systematic of application Handbook of Sociodrama for improve interpersonal communication skills junior high school students	4
6.	Completeness of Application Handbook of Sociodrama for improve interpersonal communication skills junior high school students	4
7.	Total Average	3.54
8.	Total average of quantitative assessment guidance and counseling expert judgment	3.5

From assessment of guidance and counseling expert judgment can be seen the assessment on aspect of usability, average obtained is 3.4. Assessment of aspect of easily, average obtained is 3. Assessment of aspect of accuracy, average obtained is 3.4. Assessment on aspect of attractiveness, average obtained 4. Result of total average, average obtained is 3,45. Whereas, systematic assessment handbook of sociodrama by guidance and counseling expert judgment on aspects of clarity, overall average score is 3.54. Total average on quantitative assessment obtained an average value of 3.5 in interpretation scale from guidance and counseling expert judgment explain that

handbook of sociodrama to improve communication skills of junior high school students is very useful, very easy, very accurate, very interesting, and very clear. Next, the results of assessment drama expert judgment are a format for evaluating of the development product. The result of drama expert judgment is as follows:

Table 3: Assessment of Sociodrama scenario by Drama Expert Judgment

No.	Rated Aspect	Average
1.	Accuracy	2.7
2.	Usability	2
3.	Clarity	2.3
4.	Attractiveness	2
5.	Importance of reflective to know the success of application of Sociodrama	3
6.	Completeness of Sociodrama scenario	2
7.	Total Average	2.33

From assessment of drama expert judgment, it is known that the assessment on aspect of accuracy, average obtained is 2.7. Assessment on aspects of usability, average obtained is 2. Assessment on aspect of clarity, average obtained is 2.3. Assessment on aspect of attractiveness, average obtained is 2. Total average in quantitative assessment obtained an average value of 2.33 in interpretation scale from guidance and counseling expert judgment explain that sociodrama scenario to improve communication skills of junior high school students is quite accurate, quite easy, quite clear, and quite interesting. Next, the result of media expert judgment is as follows:

Table 4: Assessment of Media by Media Expert Judgment

No.	Rated Aspect	Average
1.	Accuracy and attractiveness of cover structure	3.13
2.	Accuracy and attractiveness of preface	3.75
3.	Accuracy and attractiveness of table of contents	3.95
4.	Accuracy and attractiveness of introduction	3.7
5.	Accuracy and attractiveness of application handbook	4
6.	Accuracy and attractiveness of Sociodrama scenario	3.9
7.	Accuracy and attractiveness of evaluation	4
8.	Accuracy and attractiveness of closing	3.9
9.	Accuracy and attractiveness of appendix	4
10.	Accuracy and attractiveness of writing page number	4
11.	Accuracy and attractiveness of advice words	4
12.	Accuracy and attractiveness of cover type paper	3
13.	Accuracy and attractiveness of cover content of handbook	3
14.	Accuracy and attractiveness of handbook size	3
15.	Total average of quantitative assessment media expert judgment	3.7

From assessment of media expert judgment, can be seen that the assessment of the aspect of accuracy and attractiveness with a total average is 3.7 in interpretation scale from guidance and counseling expert judgment explain that handbook of sociodrama to improve communication skills of junior high school students is very accurate and very

attractiveness. Assessment of product user expert judgment (counselor) is assessment format part I and II from product development. Data from product user expert judgment (counselor) are as follows:

Table 5: Assessment of Product Specification by Product User Expert Judgment

No.	Rated Aspect	Average
1.	Usability	3.7
2.	Easily	3.7
3.	Accuracy	3.6
4.	Attractiveness	3
5.	Total Average	3.5

Table 6: Systematic Assessment Handbook of Sociodrama by Product User Expert Judgment

No.	Rated Aspect	Average
1.	Introduction	3.33
2.	Application handbook of Sociodrama	3.3
3.	Sociodrama scenario	3.5
4.	Closing and evaluation	3.25
5.	Systematic of application Handbook of Sociodrama for improve interpersonal communication skills junior high school students	3.5
6.	Completeness of application Handbook of Sociodrama for improve interpersonal communication skills junior high school students	4
7.	Total Average	3.48
8.	Total average of quantitative assessment product user expert judgment	3.49

From assessment of product user expert judgment can be seen the assessment on aspect of usability, average obtained is 3.7. Assessment of aspect of easily, average obtained is 3.7. Assessment of aspect of accuracy, average obtained is 3.6. Assessment on aspect of attractiveness, average obtained is 3. Result of total average, average obtained is 3,5. Whereas, systematic assessment handbook of sociodrama by product user expert judgment on aspects of clarity, overall average score is 3.48. Total average on quantitative assessment obtained an average value of 3.49 in interpretation scale from product user expert judgment explain that handbook of sociodrama to improve communication skills of junior high school students is very useful, very easy, very accurate, very interesting, and very clear..

4.2 Qualitative Data from Expert Judgment

Qualitative data from guidance and counseling expert judgment are obtained from a written assessment in the section of assessment instrument suggestion when testing products and input in handbook of sociodrama. Qualitative data from guidance and counseling expert judgment are as follows:

Table 7: Suggestion from Guidance and Counseling Expert Judgment

No.	Revised Section	Form of Suggested Revision
1.	Chapter I (Introduction)	The form of sentence arrangement is not in accordance with the correct spelling (Subject - Predicate - Object - Information), the sentence arrangement is still wrong, there is an incorrect statement, the contents of the evaluation component are still not correct.
2.	Chapter II (Application Handbook of Sociodrama)	Writing words is still wrong, the sentence still needs to be corrected and there are incomplete sentences
3.	Chapter III (Sociodrama Scenario)	On page 22 in the handbook of sociodrama (try to avoid any advice), the stage is less clear, reflection discussion is not to measure success, but rather to explain the acquisition or knowledge of student learning
4.	Bab IV (Evaluation)	There are ambiguous sentences.
5.	Appendix	What is the position of this scenario in this guide? Example: in the fourth scene, the part of the story is irrelevant; evaluation is associated with the sociodrama process. Problem solving does not always involve the teacher.

Qualitative data from drama expert judgment are obtained from a written assessment of the sociodrama scenario and the assessment instrument suggestion when testing products. Qualitative data from drama expert judgment are as follows:

Table 8: Suggestion from Drama Expert Judgment

No.	Revised Section	Form of Suggested Revision
1.	Attractiveness of Sociodrama	Attractiveness about staging is still considered (humor, etc.)
2.	Problems raised	Student problems need to be overcome in staging
3.	Evaluation in a sociodrama scenario	Evaluate the source of the problem from the show (sociodrama scenario)
4.	Topics raised in staging must be in accordance with the analysis of the problem	The performance must be in accordance with the analysis of the problem and packaged in an interesting form so that it gets the attention of students

Qualitative data from media expert judgment are obtained from a written assessment in the section of assessment instrument suggestion when testing products and input in handbook of sociodrama. Qualitative data from media expert judgment are as follows:

Table 9: Suggestion from Media Expert Judgment

No.	Revised Section	Form of Suggested Revision
1.	Writing	Quite good at developing media, but it needs to be examined in writing

Qualitative data from product user expert judgment are obtained from a written assessment of the sociodrama scenario and the assessment instrument suggestion when testing products. Qualitative data from product user expert judgment are as follows:

Table 10: Suggestion from Product User Expert Judgment

No.	Revised Section	Form of Suggested Revision
1.	Sociodrama Scenario	The contents of script's background need to contain a moral message that is in accordance with the student's development

5. Discussion

Handbook of sociodrama for improving interpersonal communication skills is a handbook that contains procedures that need to be considered by counselors in using sociodrama guidelines to improve the interpersonal communication skills of junior high school students. The contents of this handbook consist of: preface, table of contents, chapter I (introduction), chapter II (application of handbook), chapter III (sociodrama scenario), chapter IV (evaluation), chapter V (closing), reference list, and appendix.

The existence of a handbook of sociodrama to improve the complete interpersonal communication skills of junior high school students can help the provision of group guidance services using sociodrama techniques to improve student interpersonal communication skills. In playing sociodrama, students spontaneously and creatively display each sociodrama scene, and in accordance with the outline of the story raised, so that directly or indirectly there is a learning process of students in sociodrama games.

Sociodrama is a dramatization of various problems that can arise in association with others, including conflicts that are often experienced in social interaction (Kellerman, 2007; McLennan, 2008; Sternberg & Garcia, 2000). Student involvement in sociodrama becomes active in the process of role playing so as to shape new social behavior (Aryani & Farozin, 2017; Rajapaksha, 2016). By using sociodrama games can develop the skills needed, students can develop optimally (Aryani & Farozin, 2017; Riley, 1990). The handbook of sociodrama is a tool or method used by counselors to teach certain skills through modeling that is used in helping students to improve interpersonal communication skills in sociodrama, so students can communicate effectively with their peers, so there is no misunderstanding among their peers. In socializing, interpersonal communication skills are most often regarded as a set of skills that allow us to communicate, relate and socialize with others (Kewalramani & Singh, 2017; Suhaimi, A.W., Marzuki, N.A., & Mustaffa, C.S, 2014). Effective interpersonal communication skills are very important for building and maintaining relationships in social interactions (Ngong, 2014; Suhaimi, Marzuki, & Mustaffa, 2014). Poor communication skills can cause relationship damage, affect productivity, satisfaction, performance, morale, trust, respect, self-confidence, and even physical health (Arizaga, Bauman, Waldo, & Castellanos, 2005; Eroskan, 2013; Okoro, Washington & Thomas, 2017).

The aspects of usability, attractiveness, easily, and accuracy in the handbook of sociodrama can be seen from the material, procedures for application of sociodrama, and sociodrama scenario. The handbook of sociodrama was designed with attractive cover colors and was given a picture so that the cover was better, on the back of the

cover there was a synopsis of the book and the words of wisdom and developer photos, on the edge there was the title of the book for the counselor and the year of making the handbook. In each chapter in the book, there are images that are adapted to the material displayed in the sub-chapter and there are words of advice. In this handbook of sociodrama, the media used are in the form of a handbook of sociodrama for junior high school students, a training method used and implemented by counselors, as well as trained teachers. So that the activities carried out are fun and not boring, and allow students to learn with sociodrama.

The revised sociodrama guidelines are based on suggestions and input from expert tests. This product was developed through a long process, starting with the formation of a prototype, review of three experts (guidance and counseling expert judgment, media expert judgment, and drama expert judgment) and product user expert judgment (counselors), until the product was completed. The assessment of the expert judgment in the form of quantitative data, namely descriptive statistics in the form of score assessment and qualitative data in the form of suggestions from expert judgment, it can be concluded that the handbook of sociodrama to improving interpersonal communication skills is beneficial for junior high school students in providing guidance and counseling services optimally with having acceptance is very useful, very accurate, very easy, and very theoretically interesting. Whereas the media assessment of this guidebook has aspects of accuracy and attractiveness of covers, preface, table of contents, introduction, application handbook of sociodrama, sociodrama scenario, evaluation, closing, appendix, writing page number, admonition, type of cover paper, type of handbook paper, the size of the handbook, is very accurate and interesting.

This handbook of sociodrama has several advantages, namely the topic is adjusted to the needs of students, this handbook can be used by counselors in providing services to students and better understanding sociodrama techniques, and using sociodrama techniques, students can learn by playing, experiencing, practicing, and see and know about the material presented. As for the weaknesses of this product, this handbook is only for counselors

5. Recommendations

The recommendations developed are the existence of a handbook of sociodrama to improve students interpersonal communication skills, schools can facilitate it to be used as a reference in school counselors regular meetings, so that other schools can implement it by adjusting the characteristics of each school's students; counselors (product users) really understand and study this handbook of sociodrama so that it can be applied in helping students improve interpersonal communication skills by using sociodrama techniques effectively to provide guidance and counseling services; Further researchers, a handbook of sociodrama to improving interpersonal communication skills can be continued with experiments to determine the effectiveness of handbook of

sociodrama for improving interpersonal communication skills to obtain more accurate results.

6. Conclusion

From the results of the expert guidance and counseling test, it can be seen that the assessment on the aspects of usability, the average obtained is 3.4. Assessment of aspects of easily, the average obtained is 3. Assessment of aspects of accuracy, the average obtained is 3.4. Assessment on aspects of attractiveness, the average obtained is 4. From the results of the calculation of the overall average obtained an average value of 3.45. While the systematic assessment handbook of sociodrama by guidance and counseling expert judgment on aspects of clarity, the overall average score is 3.54. The overall total average in the quantitative assessment obtained an average value of 3.5 in the scale of interpretation of the results of the calculation of expert judgment, data meaning that the handbook of sociodrama to improving communication skills of junior high school students is very useful, very easy, very accurate, very interesting, and very clear.

From the results of the drama expert judgment, it can be seen the assessment of the aspect of accuracy, the average obtained is 2.7. Assessment on aspects of usability, the average obtained is 2. Assessment on aspects of clarity, the average obtained is 2.3. Assessment on the aspect of attractiveness, the average obtained is 2. From the calculation of the overall total in the quantitative assessment obtained an average value of is 2.33. The overall average value of 2.33 in the scale of interpretation of the results of the calculation of the drama expert judgment, data means that the sociodrama scenario to improve the communication skills of junior high school students is quite accurate, quite easy, quite clear, and quite interesting.

From the results of the media expert judgment, it can be seen that the assessment of the aspects of accuracy and enjoyment with an overall average value of 3.7 has the meaning that the handbook of sociodrama for improving communication skills of junior high school students is very accurate and very interesting.

From the results of the product user, expert judgment can find an assessment of the usability aspect, the average obtained is 3.7. Assessment of aspects of easily, the average obtained is 3.7. Assessment of the aspect of accuracy, the average obtained is 3.6. Assessment on aspects of attractiveness, the average obtained is 3. From the results of the calculation of the overall average obtained an average value of 3.5. While the systematic assessment of the handbook of sociodrama by product user expert judgment on aspects of clarity, the overall average score is 3.48. The overall average total in the quantitative assessment obtained an average value of 3.49 in the scale of interpretation of the results of the calculation of expert test data means that the sociodrama guide to improving communication skills of junior high school students is very useful, very easy, very accurate, very interesting, and very clear.

References

- Aryani, E. & Farozin, M. 2017. Improving Social Skill through Sociodrama Technique for Yunion High School Students, *Asian Journal of Educational Research*, 5 (1), pp. 7-20.
- Arizaga, M.P., Bauman, S., Waldo, M., & Castellanos, L.P. 2005. Multicultural Sensitivity and Interpersonal Skills Training for Preservice Teachers, *Journal of Humanistic Counseling, Education & Development*, 44 (2), 198-208.
- Barbato C.A, Graham E.E & Perse E.M. 2003. Communicating in the Family: An Examination of the Relationship of Family Communication Climate and Interpersonal Communication Motives. *Journal of Family Communication*, 3 (3), 123-148.
- Beebe, S.A., Beebe, S.J. & Redmond, V. 2010. *Interpersonal Communication*. 6th Edition. Boston: Allyn & Bacon
- Borg, W. D. & Gall, M. D. 1983. *Educational Research* Third Edition. New York: Longman Inc.
- Creswell, J.W. 2012. *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting, Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research*. Boston: Pearson.
- Eckloff, M. 2006. Using Sociodrama to Improve Communication and Understanding. *ETC: A Review of General Semantics*, 63 (3), pp. 259-69.
- Erozkan, A. 2013. The Effect of Communication Skills and Interpersonal Problem Solving Skills on Social Self-Efficacy, *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 13 (2), pp. 739-745.
- Hackman, M.Z. & C. Johnson. C.E. 2004. *Leadership: A Communication Perspective*. 4th Edition. Prospect Heights, IL: Waveland.
- Johnson, D.W. & Johnson, F.P. 1991. *Joining Together: Group Theory and Groups skills*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall Inc.
- Kellerman, P. 2007. *Sociodrama and Collective Trauma*. London: Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
- Kewalramani, S. & Singh, M.S. 2017. Relationship between Aggression and Interpersonal Communication, *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 4 (3), pp. 91-112.
- McLennan, D.P. 2008. Kinder-Caring: Exploring The Use and Effects of Sociodrama in A Kindergarten Classroom, *Journal of Student Wellbeing*, 2 (1), pp. 74-88.
- Ngong, P.A. 2014. Interpersonal and Communication Skills Development in Therapeutic Theatre, *GSTF Journal on Media & Communications (JMC)*, 2 (1), pp. 40-44.
- Okoro, E., Washington, M.C., & Thomas, O. 2017. The Impact of Interpersonal Communication Skills on Organizational Effectiveness and Social Self-Efficacy: A Synthesis, *International Journal of Language and Linguistics*, 4 (3), pp. 28-32.

- Rajapaksha, P.L.N.R. 2016. Promoting Oral Language Skills in Preschool Children through Sociodramatic Play in the Classroom, *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*, 4 (1), pp. 15-23.
- Riley, J.F. 1990. Sociodrama: Group Creative Problem-Solving in Action, *Journal of Creative Teaching*, 13 (1), pp. 28-30.
- Skinner, K.L., Hyde, S.J., & McPherson, K.B.A. 2016. Improving Students' Interpersonal Skills Through Experiential Small Group Learning, *Journal of Learning Design*, 9 (1), pp. 21-36.
- Singh, A.K. & Lalropuii. (2014). Role of Interpersonal Communication in Organizational Effectiveness. *International Journal of Research in Management and Business Studies (IJRMBS)*, 1 (4), pp. 36-39.
- Stein, S., Ingersoll, R. & Treadwell, T. 1995. Sociodrama and Professional Ethical Conflicts. *Journal of Group Psychotherapy, Psychodrama & Sociometry*, 48 (1), pp. 31-41.
- Sternberg, P. & Garcia, A. 2000. Sociodrama: Who's in your shoes? Westport, CT: Praeger.
- Suhaimi, A.W., Marzuki, N.A., & Mustaffa, C.S. 2014. The Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Interpersonal Communication Skills in Disaster Management Context: A Proposed Framework. *In International Conference on Communication and Media 2014 (i-COME'14)*, pp. 110-114.
- Zachariah, M. & Moreno, R. 2006. Finding My Place: The Use of Sociometric Choice and Sociodrama for Building Community in the School Classroom. *Journal of Group Psychotherapy, Psychodrama & Sociometry*, 58 (4), pp. 157-67.

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